

Effect of auditory thresholds on sensory and memory semantics: A functional MRI study.

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INTRODUCTION

The auditory and visual semantics are an interlinked biological mechanistic model which serves the purpose of effective communication. The interplay of auditory and visual information provides concurrent development of short-term memory (STM) and long-term memory (LTM) in an individual. The ability to memorize is dependent on association of memory to executive function for processing of information. As frequency threshold of auditory range is different across individual, they subsequently affect the memory and processing of information in complex mechanism. The current study was designed to assess the effect of auditory range (i.e., sensory response) threshold towards association of memory semantics. Furthermore, to also elucidate the nature of sensory range across which the shift in memory and sensory association is observed.

METHODOLOGY

A group of 90 Volunteers were recruited for functional and Structural MRI data acquisition and audiogram assessment such as Pure Tone assessment, Auditory Brain Stem Response (ABR).

A statistically data regression approach was utilised toward de-noising the dataset with subject motion threshold to 2mm and PTA threshold of individual within range of 45-55+ db. in higher frequency spectra were rejected.

Data acquisition was carried out using Neurosoft (PTA) and 3T Philips Ingenia for fMRI. Subject performed 1-Back and 2-Back Auditory memory tasks. A Seed to Voxel Based analysis across all subjects with Task modulation (gPPI) effect was studied. The audiometric threshold of each individual for 125Hz and 500Hz was input as modulation factor in seed to voxel analysis. Statistical analysis with voxel threshold of $P < .0001$ (uncorrected) and cluster threshold of $p < 0.05$ (corrected) was computed.

RESULT

A brief representation of network connectivity and its confounded effects associated to different audiological spectra ranges is displayed in serial order from lowest 125Hz to highest 16KHz frequency threshold effect on general memory semantics.

Also, as it can be observed from the effective seed to voxel activity associated to Language network in general is displaying a shift in network activity as a modulation effect from audiological thresholds. Wherein, 1back (memory) semantics is limited across 250,500,1K and 10K Hz. and 2back (memory) is differing from above mentioned ranges to 4K, 6K and 16K Hz.

In short term memory, shown in Table 1 and Fig. 1, as the auditory frequency threshold of individual increases, the ability of sensory processing shift from executive network (frontal pole, lingual gyrus, precuneus, cingulate gyrus and thalamus) to sensory perception (occipital pole and lateral occipital cortex) for association of information. However, the same is not true when one considers interference memory mechanisms in 2-Back condition, which have differential range from memorising and retrieval of information for memory within 500Hz spectra and retrieval at 125Hz.

Such, interplay of frequency specific effective nature can be meaningful in several govt. initiative across audio and visual aid system adaptability and reliability factor assessment, for upliftment of individual in varied range of communication.

Table 1: Seed-to-voxel analysis for language network using inferior fusiform gyrus as source region and audiometric range as modulation factor, illustrating shifts in network association from executive to sensory systems across task conditions.

Task Condition	Network activity associated with language IFG under different auditory thresholds	Auditory Threshold
1-Back (Memory)	Precuneus (precuneus cortex) PC (Cingulate gyrus, posterior division) Left Thalamus	125 Hz
	iLOC _r (Lateral occipital cortex, inferior division, right) OFusG _r (Occipital fusiform gyrus, right)	500 Hz
1-Back (Retrieval)	FP _l (Frontal pole, left) LG _r (Lingual gyrus, right) PC (Cingulate gyrus, posterior division)	125 Hz
	OFusG _r (Occipital fusiform gyrus, right) LG _l (Lingual gyrus, left)	500 Hz
2-Back (Memory)	PaCiG _l , PaCiG _r (Paracingulate gyrus, left and right)	500 Hz
2-Back (Retrieval)	pSMG _r (Supramarginal gyrus, posterior division, right); AG _r (Angular gyrus, right)	125 Hz

Figure 1: Figure: Effect of different audiological ranges on cognitive model and brain states

Future Perspective:

Current work is only a short presentation showcasing the inherent efficacies related to sound and how it merely function as a cognitive and sensory input. Its superimposing effect in general are main focus of project, where we intend to classify and in-herent effect of change in cognition or psychological impact that “Noise Pollution” have at individual level and to what extent it radiates wherein it start deteriorating the Quality of Life (QOL) as the effect becomes more repetitive.

Noise pollution does affect every individual yet no consensus has been set to what level it affects and how it can be assessed for proper ratification.

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